

Founding, Running, and Improving Scholarly Journals: A Comprehensive Look Behind the Scenes

- Findings -

Poster presented at the 45th Annual Meeting of the Society for Scholarly Publishing (SSP) in Portland, Oregon, United States of America. Poster prepared by Andrea Blatz (University of Texas Press) and Mario Pallua (Libertas International University).

We set out to see what resources exist for those who want to either start a scholarly journal or improve one. We present the results of [interviews](#) conducted with scholarly publishing professionals and an [online questionnaire](#). These evaluations aimed to determine what gaps in educational content currently exist and what obstacles scholarly publishing professionals face in terms of knowledge and access to best practices.

INTERVIEWS

We interviewed four people who work with new scholarly journals in a variety of ways:

- Journals manager at a university press that publishes 13 journals; recently acquired two new journals
- Journal manager at a scientific society's publishing arm; recently took part in search for new editor-in-chief
- Sales director at scholarly publishing company
- Journal founder, director of publishing master's program

We asked a range of questions aimed at finding out where they find answers to their questions, what tips they have for people looking to start a journal, and what they would find helpful in addition to what already exists.

How are journals started?

- UP: Work with scholars to identify gap in the field, how we can exploit it, work with scholars as editor-in-chief, once it's set up, they do most of the work
- Scientific society: Look for gap in scholarly production, then set everything up, hire editor-in-chief
 - If someone came to publisher looking to publish a journal, might consider if it's in the realm of what they covered
- Sales director: Variety of ways
 - Subject gets too big, break into more than one journal
 - Outgrowth of academic program
 - Consultants can help
 - Individuals interested in a subject
 - Some might start as newsletter, eventually grow into more structured journal
- Journal founder: Had an idea, used program for funding, did research on where to host

What are some important things to consider before starting a journal?

- It takes a lot of time!
- Do lots of research on the topic. If you don't have a good enough topic, the journal won't survive.
- The choice of editor-in-chief is also important. You should ask questions relating to what kind of networks do they have? Are they known in the field?

- You need to make sure there's a market, since you can't publish without money.
- Have a clear explanation of goals and why you want to achieve them. Write out your editorial and business plans, some ideas for who could serve as the editor-in-chief, editorial board, and submission policy.

Would you have made different choices in starting the journal?

- UP: Bringing in production team earlier would have helped shaped the path the journal was going to take.
- Scientific society: It was hard to find the right editor-in-chief, which impacted the timeline.
- Journal founder: With humanities journals, most of the work is done by volunteers, so accountability can be hard at times.

What resources already exist?

- AUP (member-only) and SSP (paid) have some resources
- There are usually a lot of institutional sources, which need to be kept updated for future people in the position
- A lot of online material (maybe too much!)
- Lots of institutional knowledge; publishing changes so quickly it would be hard to keep something up to date
- Trade bodies might have internal guidelines
- People inside the industry have great experience! Don't be afraid to ask for help

What would be helpful?

- Index of indexes would help people know where to get the journal in front of those who would benefit most from it
- More resources in general for early-career professionals
 - But over the past few years, more experienced people have started to realize this is needed and have started to invest more time and money in preparing for the future (e.g., Generations Fund in SSP)
- It wouldn't hurt to have a guide, but one difficult thing would be that every journal is different. The audience and stakeholder questions are there for all journals, but there are so many different platforms, aims, funding sources, etc, that it would be nearly impossible to address every possibility.

How do you ensure the journal will receive enough article submissions to sustain the journal for the foreseeable future?

- Working with a professional society is nice because there's a built-in audience and contributors.
- For publishers, make this part of the contract.
- Start with a small number of issues, and you can always increase as you receive more submissions.
- Calls for Papers can be useful in attracting people, since they have something to focus on rather than trying to come up with an idea for a general theme of most journals.
- Marketing and promotion are essential! You need to get the word out, which help bring in more articles.

- Bigger publishers can support small journals that might not necessarily receive a lot of submissions. They could make an investment for the long term in the hopes that it will eventually take off.

QUESTIONNAIRE

Background

The aim of the questionnaire was to find out what Editors of scholarly journals believe about the availability and accessibility of professional educational content regarding founding, running, and improving scholarly journals. For this purpose, Andrea Blatz and Mario Pallua prepared the questionnaire utilizing the [SoSci survey platform](#) and advertised it through four Scholarly Publishing Association's mailing lists and forums (the Society for Scholarly Publishing (SSP), the European Association of Science Editors (EASE), the Croatian Association for Scholarly Communication (ZNAK), and the Council of Science Editors (CSE), as well as several Facebook groups and personal contacts. You may download the full raw data of the survey on Zenodo [here](#).

Respondents

As a result, 93 Scholarly Publishing professionals working with scholarly journals completed at least part of the questionnaire, while 64 completed the full questionnaire. Only two respondents stated that they have not worked for a scholarly journal, while in terms of work experience our respondents were slanted towards the more experienced categories. In terms of country of residence, 30 respondents were from the United States of America (USA), 26 from Croatia, while 31 were from other countries spread across the globe. Either by themselves or as part of a team, 43.02% of our respondents participated in founding a new scholarly journal, while 87% worked to improve a scholarly journal.

Findings

1. *While Editors can get by with the existing educational content on scholarly journals, 80 % would greatly appreciate the existence of more and the material being more accessible.*

While 54.41% of respondents agree or strongly agree that there is enough educational material on scholarly journals and only 14.71% disagree or strongly disagree, 80.88% agree or strongly agree that the existence of more educational material would help them in their work.

The same phenomenon presents itself when Editors are asked whether the educational material is accessible to them. Here, 57.35% of respondents agree or strongly agree that they have easy access to educational material whenever they need it, while 23.53% disagree or strongly disagree. However, when asked whether more accessible educational material would help them in their work, 80% of respondents agree or strongly agree.

When asked how much access to more educational content would help them in their work on a scale of 1 to 5, only 6.67% chose 1 (not at all) or 2 (a bit), while 33.33% chose 3 (somewhat), 41.67% chose 4 (quite a bit), and 18.33% chose 5 (very much).

2. Editors believe that currently educational content is most lacking in respect to the most specific areas: founding and improving scholarly journals.

Asked in which area they believe that currently there exists the biggest deficiency in educational content relating to scholarly journals, 8% stated that it was for scholarly journals in general, 13% for running scholarly journals, while 24% stated it was for founding scholarly journals and 36% for improving scholarly journals.

3. Editors would prefer new educational content to be delivered in digital formats such as websites, online courses, comprehensive educational platforms that might combine several formats of delivering content, and video content

Asked in what format they would prefer the current gaps in educational content relating to working with scholarly journals in general to be filled, our respondents predominantly chose digital formats such as websites (67.19%), online courses (57.81%), and comprehensive educational platforms (53.13%), and video content (31.25%), while only 18.75% of respondents chose books.

4. Many Editors are willing to pay for such educational content

When asked whether they personally or their employer would be willing to pay for educational content relating to working with scholarly journals, 21% of Editors said that they would and a further 36% that they maybe would, while 28% stated that they would not and 15% that they did not know. However, when asked how much per month they would be willing to pay, only 18.52% stated that they would not be willing to pay, while 81.49% stated that they would be willing to pay, with the average respondent being willing to pay 69.44\$/month.

1. Have you previously or do you currently work for a scholarly journal? Please select one or more of the options which best describe your current and/or previous role(s).

- Editor-in-chief
- Executive Editor
- Secretary
- Editorial Board Member
- Advisory Board Member
- Graphics/Layout Editor
- Language and Proofreading Editor
- Other
- Prefer not to specify
- I have not worked for a scholarly journal

2. Have you ever taken part in founding a new scholarly journal?

- I founded a scholarly journal primarily by myself
- I was part of a team that founded a new scholarly journal
- I have not founded a new scholarly journal by myself or with a team

3. Have you ever worked to improve or been part of a team that worked to improve a scholarly journal?

- I have worked to improve a scholarly journal (primarily) myself
- I have worked to improve a scholarly journal as part of a team
- I have not worked to improve a scholarly journal

4. How many years of work experience do you have in scholarly publishing, in any capacity?

- Less than 1
- 1-2
- 3-5
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 16-20
- 21-30
- 31-40
- More than 41
- Prefer not to specify

5. What is your current country of residence?

6. Regarding my work with scholarly journals...

In order to determine whether there were any geographical discrepancies for question 6 we grouped the respondents by country of residence (The United States of America, Croatia, other countries).

6.4 Regarding my work with scholarly journals in general, more accessible educational material would help me in my work

7. In relation to my work with scholarly journals a sufficient amount of educational professional material exists and is accessible to me in the form of..

8. What specific resources do you use the most when faced with a problem or question while working with scholarly journals?	
1	Editors-in-chief
2	EASE, COPE, editor-in-chief
3	In-house style guides Websites, e.g., grammar girl, Word tips Professional network group on Facebook Google
4	Internet in general; people I met in various workshops
5	EASE materials, MET, materials,
6	Google
7	COPE and EASE resources
8	Associations
9	Ease, cope, cse, wame materals
10	Colleagues editors-in-chief; own experience
11	Google, Journal's instructions for authors
12	Hrčak, National library, Znak
13	www.abecbrasil.org.br www.scielo.org
14	ESC Editors Network group, TÜBİTAK ULAKBİM group, EASE network
15	EASE website Scientific style and format (CBE manual) Chicago Manual of Style EASE Scientific Editors' Handbook
16	Committe on Publication Ethics
17	google, online dictionaries, online style guides such as APA7 Style Guide, sample journals in the field in question
18	Articles, online books
19	Articles
20	COPE-Committee on Publication Ethics Guidelines; peers in the academic scholarly publishing area; Brazilian Association of Science Editores (ABEC Brazil) workshops and congress.
21	Articles, Textbooks, websites
22	Academic style guides Websites (diverse)
23	Mostly the mainstream style guides (New Oxford Dictionary for Writers and Editors, Scientific Style and Format, AMA Manual of Style, Publication Manual of the APA
24	Instructions for authors Mentor
25	several books on science editing by Robert A. Day, prof. Hull, Maeve O' Connor and a few others
26	Librarians
27	EASE - ask for advice from members
28	OASPA, COPE
29	Librarian specialized in the field
30	librarian n my institution which is an expert in this field
31	editor-in-chief
32	professional associations
33	editor-in-chief https://publicationethics.org/
34	Scholarly societies Books Mentors
35	Internal documents; work colleagues; industry colleagues
36	EASE, COPE, WAME, Elsevier, Wiley
37	My professional network
38	advice from peers and senior staff

39	repository consultants professional colleagues, co-editors peer publications and websites of related journals
40	workplace colleagues style manuals, e.g., our in-house style manual and the AMA Manual of Style
41	As the editor of a medical journal, I often look at JAMA or NEJM. SSP and ALPSP are good sources of information. Experienced colleagues are also a good source.
42	youtube! all sorts of people
43	Online resources such as SSP On Demand Colleagues, I work at a commercial publisher and they are my best resource
44	Publisher resources Webinars from SSP, CSE, and similar organizations COPE resources and COPE forum CSE web resources C4DISC web resources Online communities hosted by SSP, CMSS, and CESSE Scholarly Kitchen blog Enewsletters--The Brief, The Geysler, Journalology Personal network
45	coworkers, publisher, editor-in-chief, managing editor
46	Peer support through my professional network
47	I work at the largest scholarly global publisher, so can turn to colleagues to find the answers. I also use scholarly organizational materials, like COPE, ICMJE, SSPE
48	Publisher resources, other journal's resources for reviewers and editors, COPE, NICE, STROBE and others
49	Webiste pages search Blogs
50	EASE website https://ease.org.uk/
51	Using my existing knowledge; asking peers through SSP, LPC, or AUPresses Listserv. The Library Publishing Curriculum. Scholarly Kitchen blog.
52	COPE, ICMJE, ISTME, SSP, manager (Senior Director of Resources, Tools, and Scholarship), editor-in-chief, my organization's leadership team (e.g., Chief Academic Officer, Chief Legal Officer, Chief of Staff)
53	Editor-in-chief
54	publisher editor-in-chief Scholarly Kitchen OASPA
55	Mediterranean Editors and Translators website EASE handbook for editors
56	EASE WAME
57	managing editor clarivate how-to audit trail
58	My network of other government employees in scholarly publishing, CENDI, COPE
59	I often reach out to other scholarly publishing professionals. SSP, ISMTE, CSE web sites
60	PubMed, Lexus Nexus, JSTOR, CMOS, Oxford Style Manual, AMA Manual of Style, How to Copoyedit Scientific Books and Journa.s (Maeve O'Connor
61	Scholarly Kitchen Mentor Manager
62	Articles Webinars Peers
63	Web search

9. Regarding my work with **founding** scholarly journals...

10. Regarding my work with **running** scholarly journals...

11. Regarding my work with **improving** scholarly journals...

12. If you have worked to improve a scholarly journal, please briefly explain how you define "improve" and the actions you took to improve it.

1	Use of digital tools for the registration of authors and scientific papers
2	Improving in the sense of scientific criteria, objectivity, impartiality
3	Improve=being better indexed; I tried to follow instructions by given by databases most important in our field of science
4	better (easier) communication with the authors, improvement of technical aspects
5	Making changes in production workflow aimed to speed up the process, implemented technological algorithms and standards within the editorial which shortened the time between the acceptance and the publishing of a paper.
6	Development of online submission system, implementation of DOI and CC licence, XML formatting, plagiarism scan, redesigning journal website, layout and cover, asking authors to write authorship contribution, specify funding and use ORCID
7	Adding novelties in the editorial policie
8	indexing
9	Provide more data relevant to the journal visibility, authors' identification (e.g. adding ORCID IDs); adjusting the journal's characteristics so it will enter relevant citation bases, looking into better design solution so the journal be easier to use, ...
10	more different reviewers, plagiarism system, Open Journal System, indexing
11	More knowledge
12	Mainly implementation of new guidelines regarding scientific publications (peer review, ethics, accessibility etc.). In addition: improving layout, editorial procedures etc.
13	Increase circulation. Increase citations. Improve peer reputation. Improve the quality of commentaries and research papers
14	improve the journal is make it more efficient and competitive: i) make it more accessible to readers (which we did through unrestricted open access); ii) improve communication with authors (faster and more consistent responses); iii) enhance the attractiveness of topics and authors of high relevance to the academic community (for example, through calls for papers; iv) improve the editorial content through a more rigorously peer review process (with an area editor + two ad hoc evaluators, guidance for agile desk rejection and diligence in improving the article); v) agility in publication (for example, with a continuous flow of article publication); vi) ensure content that contributes to the advancement of science and advancement in society

	and organizations; vii) adherence to the state of the art in academic publishing (SDGs, Open Science, New Technologies, etc.) etc.
15	Improved statistical reporting by using statistical reviewers
16	My efforts have focussed on trying to improve the visibility and accessibility of our museum publications. When I first arrived, these did not include ISSN or ISBN numbers, or cataloguing metadata. I also pushed for using explicit copyright agreements with our contributors.
17	Improve the quality of reviews, increase the number of articles
18	broadening the Editorial Board, their expertise and more involvement in peer reviewing; meticulous peer review process; asking the authors for raw data provided to reviewers, rejecting poor work etc.
19	Intruduction of web based mangerial system, established clear guidelines for reviewers and authors, keeping up with the requirements of WOS and SCOPUS
20	Better instructions for authors, PEMs, visibility. Usually improvement comes after the checking process and the feedback from our skilled librarian, which is at the Institution only valuable source of information and support. Or when we went to enter databases but then is quite to late.
21	implementing ORCID, redesign, DOAJ, unifying citation
22	Improve in terms of raising journal's visibility and citations
23	Ethical principles, review process, citation databases
24	Improve means update traditional, conservative, and elitist policies of scientific journals
25	Updated the Instructions to authors, wrote reviewer templates, implemented checks, promoted the journal
26	Open access, impact factor, DOI
27	Improvement in the form of higher submission rate, shorter reviewing process, funds acquiring, indexing. My actions on improving journal - application for funding, application for indexing, forming a contact database to send out review requests and call for papers ...e
28	Editorial practices, including more direct contact and communication with authors
29	To cite one example, I worked with my colleagues, the journal editors, and our publication service vendor to improve the presentation of figures.
30	Trying to get PMC indexing showed us areas for improvement.
31	improving peer review to make easier for authors is an example. Going role by role. All sorts of things.
32	writing policies, finding reviewers, training editors
33	It depends on the journal and its situation--some examples include improving efficiency in the editorial office, improving author experience, improving reviewer experience, diversifying editorial boards, launching new content development initiatives, etc.
34	help with composition of editorial board, write instructions to authors, manage APCs, manage submissions and peer review
35	Worked in marketing to improve submissions and increase subscriptions.
36	strategy sessions in which we brainstorm the problems facing the community of authors and readers and solutions that we canmake available in the journals
37	Helping to support the coommunity in better metadata administration
38	lpmrove means that we have prepared better instructions for authors and reviewers, better organized website of the journal, submitted journal for inclusion in databases, made clear statements of ethical issues and archiving policy
39	Process and workflow improvement
40	Improve efficiency in peer review and submission-to-publication timelines. Leveraged submission and peer review data as well as HR/time management data to identify benchmarks and goals and ensure that staff were calibrated in the time spent on tasks; implemented new workflows in the peer review management system to centralize tasks in some cases and decentralize them in others; identified gaps in our data tracking and began collecting new data as needed to inform policies and processes.
41	Listing in new databases, indexes, DOI number, meta data
42	quicker turnaround time through better organization; higher impact factor through stricter acceptance standards
43	I worked on improving its visibility and on improving the quality of published papers, which ensured a steady flow of quality authors and higher citation
44	By improve I mean both on the backend (streamlining our processes) and on the front end (increasing diversity of authors and subject matters). I work primarily on the backend by

	overseeing and cleaning up our ScholarOne database. But I also track submissions by area/topic and have been working to bring certain submissions to greater prominence to the editors.
45	better impact, better accessibility, more ways to disseminate (audio, video, visual abstracts, plain language summaries, etc.)
46	Using the right technology for online presence and getting DOI for journals I manage for my university. Prior to my involvement, WordPress was used to develop journal websites but we migrated to OJS when I got involved.

13. In which area do you believe that currently there exists the biggest deficiency in educational content relating to scholarly journals?

■ Scholarly journals in general
 ■ Founding scholarly journals
 ■ Running scholarly journals
 ■ Improving scholarly journals
 ■ Don't know

14. In what format or formats would you prefer the current gaps in educational content relating to working with scholarly journals in general to be filled? Please select all that apply.

- Online material not published in book, article, or course format (websites)
- Books
- Articles
- Online courses
- In-person training
- Video content
- Audio content
- Comprehensive educational platforms
- My institution's internal documents
- Better peer support at my workplace
- Better peer support through professional associations
- Better peer support through my professional network
- Other

15. How much would access to more educational content related to your work with scholarly journals help you in your work?

- Not at all (1)
- A bit (2)
- Somewhat (3)
- Quite a bit (4)
- Very much (5)

16. Would you or your employer be willing to pay for such educational content related to your work with academic journals?

17. How much would you or your employer be willing to pay for educational content related to your work with academic journals per month?

18. Do you have any final thoughts relating to professional development content and/or your work with scholarly journals?

1	The situation for the humanities and its journals isn't good.
2	Financial support needed to ensure development of journal quality.
3	Professional associations and their regularly sending of information are very important; it would also be important to change the time when our Ministry of science decides about the money for scholarly journals - the end of the year, for the current year... Ministry of culture for example does that at the beginning of the year.
4	development of scholarly journals have to be in line with the general changes in the area of scholarly publishing and data dissemination. Acquisition of more and more data sets new tasks for the journal in selection and transmission of information to the scientific community.
5	It would be good to have some advices on journal financing opportunities and business models
6	None
7	I would appreciate it very much if people who are in top positions in local and national professional associations would pay more respect to differences that exist among the journals of different scholarly fields, instead of forcing standards from STEM, medicine and information sciences to journals from humanities. The latter are frequently belittled and their needs have

	been constantly ignored (and I say this from many years of experience) by these persons. Citation data bases as well as professional associations must have more sensibility for specificities of journals publishing in humanities (and in historical sciences in particular).
8	the institution should be more interested in maintaining and improving the journal
9	No
10	/
11	I believe that professionals in the area need more structured training, not necessarily an undergraduate course, but a course that gives them knowledge and repertoire to deal with complex everyday situations.
12	Our museum has not had any technical audit of how its journals and website could be improved. We are a multilingual research institution based in Japan. Despite making huge efforts to publish in English and other non-Japanese languages, basic technical issues were overlooked. The first 20-30 years of publishing effort were thus effectively invisible to the world. I have been able to help, but improvements have been piecemeal and non-systematic.
13	There are many new emerging and rather aggressive publishers, promising to publish articles in 37 days from submission, having them reviewed within a week etc. And then in such article one finds completely incorrectly cited articles, terms such as colorimetric incorrectly written as calorimetric etc. We never encounter fraud, heavy errors or negligence in science writing back in the 1970s and 1980s. The authors were not asked to pay huge amounts of money as APF, the reviews were paid a small honorarium for their extra work. I dislike very much the present pressures on authors, often the superficial science and science writing, the huge numbers of unnecessary articles that bringing no new knowledge just enlarge the number of articles. The open access model has brought the dark side of humans who are misung it by "founding" the predatory journals. Things in science badly need some kind of profound change to renew the higest quest for truth.
14	I suggest making a collaborative book, similar that has been done by JEDI or EASE.
15	Point of need content most helpful
16	While I think there is adequate resources available for starting a journal, a clearinghouse of information would be helpful.
17	Every journal is quite different, has a unique culture. There is no one best practice. There cannot be. The whole assumption behind this survey is flawed! sorry!
18	Professional associations sometimes do not realize that publishers are competitors, and those who work for for-profit companies have strict rules about sharing information. Societies often compete with each other as well, with unwritten rules about which societies one can share with.
19	The Society for Scholarly Publishing is my primary resource for material of this nature.
20	It is helpful when you have completed the professional development to have a certificate or something similar to ASAE certification
21	I tend to think that such content is a common interest to journals and publishers. Instead of every journal having one, there should be a open access common educational platform for all journal editors, reviewers.
22	I'm frustrated with the "per page" instead of "per hour" pay rates, since much of what I do is edit articles by non-native English speakers. Sometime doing an adequate job puts me at minimum wage.
23	Best practices are needed